

ppm. Abasal dose of one-third N and a full dose of P and K were applied at the time of transplanting and the remaining two-thirds applied in two split doses after 20 and 40 d after transplanting (DAT).

A significant increase in number of effective panicles (at 55 DAT), plant height (at 55 DAT), and grain yield (g pot⁻¹) was observed with the integrated treatment combination (T2) vs the full dose of fertilizer alone (T1). Treatment T2 (two-thirds N through fertilizer + one-third N through VC) was on a par with T3 (three-fourths N through fertilizer + one-fourth N through VC) (Table 1). A significant increase in N uptake was also found with treatment T2.

When inorganic fertilizer was added in soil along with organic manure, the availability of N in the form of ammoniacal N continued to be higher for a longer period (Table 2), showing better compatibility and efficiency of combined organic and inorganic sources. Agronomic efficiency in terms of increase in grain yield (g) per gram of

Table 1. Effect of different combinations of VC and fertilizer N on rice. Uttar Pradesh, India. 1994 wet season.

Treatment	Effective panicles (no.) (55 DAT)	Plant height (cm) (55 DAT)	Grain yield (g pot ⁻¹)	Straw yield (g pot ⁻¹)	N in straw (%)	N in grain (%)	N uptake (g pot ⁻¹)
T0 Control	7.4	51.0	6.5	9.8	0.42	0.85	0.10
T1 Full dose N through fertilizer	20.0	57.6	16.1	24.7	0.61	1.12	0.34
T2 2/3 N (fertilizer) + 1/3 N (VC)	24.6	62.4	18.6	26.2	0.65	1.19	0.38
T3 3/4 N (fertilizer) + 1/4 N (VC)	23.1	61.3	17.8	27.6	0.63	1.16	0.38
LSD (0.05)	3.1	3.8	1.8	2.4	0.07	0.09	0.04

added N was 18 for fertilizer N and 21 for fertilizer N + VC, whereas the values of physiological efficiency in terms of increase in grain yield (g) per gram of increase in N uptake were 40 for fertilizer N and 44 for fertilizer N + VC.

Combined application of inorganic fertilizer (two-thirds N) and VC (one-third N) is promising for better fertilizer management. Before making recommendations, the performance of these combinations must be evaluated in farmers' fields. ■

Table 2. Release pattern of NH₄⁺-N under waterlogged conditions.

Treatment	NH ₄ ⁺ -N (ppm)		
	7 d	14 d	21 d
Control	38.74	43.05	45.74
100 ppm N through (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	118.75	123.10	125.73
100 ppm N through VC	72.65	106.48	119.07
75 ppm N through (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ + 25 ppm N through VC	124.62	130.49	135.61
50 ppm N through (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ + 50 ppm N through VC	122.75	129.01	136.61
25 ppm N through (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ + 75 ppm N through VC	96.62	118.61	128.02

Integrated pest management—diseases

Two Myanma isolates of rice tungro bacilliform virus belong to the Southeast Asian strain

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Rice tungro is one of the most devastating rice diseases in South and Southeast Asia. It is caused by two viruses, rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). RTBV is responsible for symptom development. Its transmission by leafhopper depends on RTSV which, by itself, does not cause marked symptoms.

Two strains of RTBV have been reported previously, one from the Indian subcontinent, the other from Southeast Asia. The nearest that two RTBV strains were found is Assam in India, Dhaka in Bangladesh (Indian strain), and central Thailand, a distance of about 1500 km. These two regions are not separated by a rice-free area; Myanmar produces considerable rice. Although tungro has been suspected to occur in Myanmar, it has not been identified there. We were interested in seeing which RTBV strain can be found in Myanmar.

Samples with tungro symptoms were collected from the fields around Yangon (Baular, Hlegu, Central Rice Model Farm, Tookying) and around Mandalay (Pathenlay, Amarapura, and

Kankank). The quick assay for differentiation of strains is by polymerase chain reaction (PCR), around a 64-bp deletion, which is characteristic for the Indian strain. Degenerate primer sequences used for PCR are as follows: direct 5'-GAASAAGTACCATGACCATGAATACN (position 7743-7763 in RTBV genome) and reverse 5'-CACCCCGGGKRWNGCTCTGATACCA (position 17-1 in RTBV genome). The ambiguities are K = G or T, M = A or C, R = A or G, S = C or G, and W = A or T. PCR results have shown that samples collected near Mandalay (Amarapura) and Yangon (Baular) are infected with RTBV; we were not able to detect RTBV in other samples. The size of the PCR products is 280 bp, which indicates no

deletion and that the Myanma RTBV isolates belong to the Southeast Asian strain.

PCR products of both isolates were sequenced directly using the same PCR primers. Nucleotide sequences were compared with other RTBV isolates (see figure). Only 3 positions (7765, 7768, and 7855), which represent only 1.5% of the region sequenced, of both isolates, were different from the published sequence of the Philippine isolate. The Indian isolate differs significantly from other Southeast Asian isolates, the homology being less than 80%. The Baular isolate has a transition of T (C at position 7853 and a deletion at position 7956, a structure that differentiates it from the Amara-pura and other isolates. Ambiguities found at positions 7858, 7870, 7921, 7945, and 7949 may reflect the level of variation of the virus within the isolate. This information is only found if PCR products of viral DNA are sequenced, because cloning would result in selection of only one variant per clone.

These results demonstrate that tungro is present in Myanmar. The symptoms were characteristic of the disease and occurred in patches in the fields. The results also support the versatility of this PCR approach in the identification of RTBV itself and the strain of the virus. ■

	7758				7806
JII	AATACCCT.A	TAGATGTTAG	AAGGAAGATA	CGAACTAAGT	TTCTTATGAA
JAP	AATACCCT.A	TAGATGTTAG	AAGGAAGATA	AGAACTAAGT	ATCTTATGAA
MY6	AATACCCT.A	TAGATGTTAG	AAGGAAGGTA	GGAACTAAGT	ATCTTATGAA
BEA	AATACCCT.A	TAGATGTTAG	AAGGAAGATG	AGAACTAAGT	ATCTTATGAA
MY10	AATACCCT.A	TAGATGTTAG	AAGGAAGGTA	GGAACTAAGT	ATCTTATGAA
IND	AATACCCTAA	TAAGTGCTAG	AAGGAAGATA	AGAACTAACG	AAATAAGGAA
	7807				7854
JII	CAATGGGTAG	CTGATTTCTG	ATTATCATT	ACAAGTA..T	CGTTATAATC
JAP	CAATGGGTAG	CTGATTTCTG	ATTATCATT	ACAAGTA..C	CGTTATAATC
MY6	CAATGGGTAG	CTGATTTCTG	ATTATCATT	ACAAGTA..T	CGTTATAATC
BEA	CAATGGGTAG	CTGATTTCTG	ATTATCATT	ACAAGTA..T	CGTTATAATC
MY10	CAATGGGTAG	CTGATTTCTG	ATTATCATT	ACAAGTA..T	CGTTATAATC
IND	CATTGGGTAG	CTGTTTCTG	ATTATCATT	TCAAGTAGCT	CTTCCTCATC
	7855				7903
JII	CATAAGCTTT	GAAAGATCTG	.CTAGTGTGG	ATACCAAAG	GCTGTCGTGG
JAP	CATAAGCTTT	GAAAGATCTG	.CTAGTGTGG	ATACCAAAG	GCTGTCGTGG
MY6	TATRAGCTTT	GAAAGTCTG	.CTAGTGTGG	ATACCAAAG	GCTGTCGTGG
BEA	CATAAGCTTT	GAAAGATCTG	.CTAGTGTGG	ATACCAAAG	GCTGTCGTGG
MY10	TATRAGCTCT	GAAAGTCTG	.CTAGTGTGG	ATACCAAAG	GCTGTCGTGG
IND	ACGAAAACCTG	CAAAGGCTG	CCAACCCTAG	GCTGAAAACAG	TGACTAGGCC
	7904				7953
JII	TTCGCCAGT	CGACGGATGA	GGTCATAAAC	GAAGCACTAG	TAGGTAACCTA
JAP	TTCGCCAGT	CGACGGATGA	GGTCATAAAC	GAAGCACTAG	TAGGTAACCTA
MY6	TTCGCCAGT	CGACGGAYGA	GTTATAAAC	GAAGCACTAG	TMGGTWACTA
BEA	TTCGCCAGT	CGACGGATGA	GGTCATAAAC	GAAGCACTAG	TAGGTAACCTA
MY10	TTCGCCAGT	CGACGGATGA	GTTATAAAC	GAAGCACTAG	TAGGTAACCTA
IND	GAGGAATTGC	GAAAAGATAG	GGGGGTGCC	GCATC.....
	7954				7892
JII	AGAGGCTTA	GGGATGAAGCA	ACGAGAAAA		
JAP	AGAGGCTTA	GGGATGA.GCA	ACGAGAAAA		
MY6	AGAGGCTTA	GGGATGA.GCA	ACGAGAAAA		
BEA	AGAGGCTTA	GGGATGA.GCA	ACGAGAAAA		
MY10	AGAGGCTTA	AGGATGA.GCA	ACGAGAAAA		
IND

Nucleotide sequence comparison across the positions 7758-7982. JII, JAP, and BEA are published sequences of RTBV isolates from the Philippines. IND is unpublished sequence of RTBV isolate from India (West Bengal), MY6 is the Amara-pura isolate, and MY10 is the Baular isolate. White letters indicate differences found in isolates from Myanmar; bold letters are ambiguities expressed as IUB codes found in the sequences of PCR products.

Hinosan (0.05%): an ecofriendly fungicide for managing rice sheath blight

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Sheath blight (ShB) is a major fungal disease of rice in northeastern India. There are no ShB-resistant varieties for that region, so chemical management is used. Recently, more attention has been paid to chemicals that would not have a negative impact on microorganisms endogenous to the rice crop ecosystem.

In 1994 and 1995, we screened fungicides known to be effective against ShB

but harmless to *Trichoderma harzianum* (Th), which is a well-known biocontrol agent of the causal agent of ShB, *Rhizoctonia solani*.

Seven fungicides were tested: Atemi 50 SL (cyproconazole), Bavistin 50 WP (carbendazim), Contaf (hexaconazole), Indofil M-45 (75% mancozeb), Hinosan (50%, edifenphos), Rhizolex 50 WP (tolelofoxmethyl), and Validacin 3L (validamycin). Treatments included recommended doses and half doses, which were tested in vitro and in vivo.

Results of the in vitro experiment indicated that, except for 0.05% Hinosan (8% inhibition), all fungicides showed inhibited Th within the range

of 31.8-92%. Hinosan (0.05%) showed no significant difference in inhibition and was equivalent to the control. When tested against the pathogen in vitro, all fungicides, including Hinosan (0.05%), showed significant inhibition compared with the untreated control (see table).

In the following winter rice seasons (Jun-Nov) of 1994 and 1995, two field trials were conducted on rainfed transplanted rice. Variety IR50 was selected and planted in two lines (20 × 15 cm) for each treatment with 2-m rows replicated three times.

In the first trial (A), the same fungicides, doses, and concentrations